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ANALYSIS OF QUALITY AS AN OBJECT OF GRAIN GRINDING
PROCESS CONTROL

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Annotation. *Grain grinding is a crucial process in the food industry, transforming raw grains into flour, which forms the foundation for various food products. This process requires precise control to achieve optimal quality in the final product. This article examines the analysis of quality as an object of grain grinding process control, delving into the key aspects of quality assessment, the factors influencing quality, and the implementation of effective control strategies.*

Using high-tech methods and high-performance equipment in enterprises to ensure the maximum output of high-quality finished products with high efficiency of grain use, implementation of digital technologies in the management of the processing possible.

Key words: *individual machines, technological systems, high-performance, equipment in enterprises, the quality, initial wheat.*

Introduction. Flour production plants consist of three main departments: Elevator; Preparation; Grain grinding departments. In the grain crushing department, a multi-stage mechanical grinding process of wheat is carried out, during which it is separated from endosperm pieces and husks. These operations are carried out on shaft devices in the entoleator, sieves [1].

The efficiency of individual machines, technological systems and the entire crushing process is a function of many factors. The main ones are: the quality of initial wheat, the condition of the working bodies of the technological machines (the degree of impermeability of the riffles, the condition of the sieves), the relative humidity of the air, etc.

It is necessary to stabilize the following parameters in the management of the technological process in the grain crushing department: consumption of wheat supplied to the threshing department; initial wheat moisture; consumption of intermediate products; varieties of flour.

Input parameters of the grain crushing department : quality indicators of wheat (type, moisture, consumption).

Production parameters : flour quality , output by varieties. Disturbing factors: product properties, technological and transport equipment characteristics, microclimate change in production buildings, voltage fluctuations in the electrical network.

The internal disturbing effects caused by the devices are: changes in the characteristics of the internal organs of the machine, bending of the teeth, clogging of the sieves, weakening of the conveyor belts of the machine. Internal disturbing factors

related to the change of microclimate of the production rooms affect the character of wheat sifting and grinding.

A change in relative air humidity from 50 to 60% reduces the electrical potential of the sieves from 12000 V to 0. Disturbances caused by the supply network are associated with $\pm 0.4\%$ fluctuation of voltage and current frequency. The change in the rotation frequency of the asynchronous motor is especially noticeable in sieves.

The control effects of the grain crushing department are the change of the tension between the shafts of the shaft machines, the change of the kinematic parameters of the shaft machine and the sieve, and the degree of opening of various adjusting barriers.

Corrective effect is shown on shaft machines and executive mechanisms for operational management. Depending on the type of control object in flour production, the nature of operational control effects is also different. By changing the position of the supply barriers and the working distance in individual machines and technological blocks, shaft machines, the operative control effect is exerted on the control object.

Control of the technological process in the grain grinding department is carried out by changing the working mode of the shaft machine-sieve of the technological block, as well as by influencing the input parameters of the object: consumption and quality of raw materials. The main device of the mill is the control effects developed in the grinding department using the shaft machine [2].

By changing the distance between the shafts, the shaft machine can be operationally controlled. The following kinematic parameters can be varied as well .

$$1) \text{ The ratio of the speed of the shafts : } K = \frac{\vartheta_T}{\vartheta_C}$$

$$2) \Delta\vartheta = \vartheta_T - \vartheta_C$$

ϑ_T - the speed of the rotating shaft; ϑ_C - slow rotating shaft speed; $\Delta\vartheta$ - speed difference.

Valli machine work is evaluated according to the dispersed composition of the product passing through the working zone.

The generalized indicator of the granulometric composition of the product - extraction A(%) is determined by the ratio of the amount of G - product passed through a sieve of a certain number to the initial sample mass:

$$A = \frac{G}{m_n}$$

In addition, the work of the shaft machine is evaluated by separate fractions of free energy and the comparative consumption of energy.

The dependence of separation A on the gap between the shafts is expressed exponentially :

$$A = m \cdot e^{-nb}$$

In this case: m – e is the coefficient y ent depending on the conditions of filtering the product in the lacdon analyzer ; n – the coefficient y ent depending on the structural-mechanical properties of wheat and grinding conditions ; v - the distance between the shafts , mm.

The output of individual fractions during grinding is also dependent on the distance between the shafts. External and internal disturbing effects change the value of n - coefficient to a certain extent.

It is not possible to carry out operational control on the connection $A=f(v)$, because the distance between the shafts - the gap - can not be measured in the shaft machine during the work process. For him, A - controlling effects are selected according to the main output value of extraction.

In the technological scheme, the position of the shaft of the machine affects the output of individual fractions depending on the A -separation.

input quantities on the kinematic parameters of the shaft machine is characterized as follows:

The change in the speed of the fast-rotating shafts has almost no effect on the output and quality of the fractions. Grinding the output of flour in the system increases significantly. If v_T - increases from 4 to 10 m/s, its output increases by 13...15%.

$K = \frac{v_T}{v_C}$ has a significant impact on the total extraction, the output of individual fractions, the quality of individual products, and the comparative consumption of electricity. If $K > 2.5$, as a result, the output of small fractions increases, ash content increases. When $K > 2.5$, the quality of small fractions decreases significantly, when the gap between the shafts increases when the riffs are bent, the adjustment ability of this factor gradually decreases, when the riffs are bent by 40%, the adjustment ability disappears completely.

Comparatively, the effect of loading on the total extraction and the output of individual fractions is significant and is expressed as an increase in loading for each kg/h at an increase in extraction of 0.1%. As a result of these increases, the quality of flour and intermediate products does not change. It is difficult to use these parameters to control the grinding process, because it is necessary to ensure the continuity of the technological process in the grinding department when changing the load.

The main tasks of automatic control of processes in grain processing enterprises are:

- increasing labor productivity as a result of reducing the number of service employees;
- increase production;
- releasing people from work in areas with difficult conditions (loud noise, a lot of dust in the air);
- increase work culture;
- technological process improvement;
- increase product quality;

- reducing energetic activities;
- increasing the operability of management, and as a result, the equipment works in the optimal mode.

The operating life of the systems working in the optimal mode will be extended, and the costs spent on providing repair services will be reduced.

Automatic control of grain processing processes is based on the automation of the main and auxiliary operations of the technological process.

Grain processing processes are suitable objects for automation, because the main technological processes are continuous and automated to a certain extent.

The goal of using information and communication technologies in the management of technological processes in grain processing enterprises is to improve economic efficiency and working conditions.

The technological process of wheat flour extraction is the separation of the endosperm from the husk and processing until the product is conditioned[11].

In the process of making flour, wheat is subjected to hydrothermal treatment, and after that, the endosperm of wheat is separated from the husk with multi-stage mechanical effects. endosperm fragments contain several shells and they are crushed in the necessary sizes.

At the last stage, flour is separated into varieties from its elementary streams.

Flour production plants consist of three main departments: 1) Elevator , 2) Preparation, 3) Filling departments [11] .

In the elevator department, wheat is received, separated according to quality indicators, the temperature is controlled during wheat storage, and components are selected for the mixtures to be crushed. Among the technological operations in the elevator : wheat cleaning and drying for individual batches are carried out.

In the preparation department, the components of the mixture to be crushed are cleaned, treated with heat and moisture, mixed in certain proportions, and sent to crushing in a single flow.

In the threshing department, a multi-stage mechanical threshing process of wheat is carried out, in which endosperm is separated from pieces and husks. These operations are carried out in the entoleator and sieves in the shaft devices.

The main technological task of the threshing department is to separate the endosperm pieces from the shells and grind them to a flour dispersion. This issue is solved in technological processes with the help of devices and sieves.

the welding department are divided into six stages according to their functional characteristics [11] :

The first stage (grinding process) separates pieces with a large amount of wheat endosperm and is threshed. This is done in a cascade of technological systems.

In the second stage, the grains are enriched in sieves and polished.

In the third stage, first-quality enriched groats and dust are ground in three grinding systems. High quality flour is obtained.

At the fourth stage, second-quality groats and dust are crushed.

In the fifth stage, second-quality groats and dusts are processed in turn.

In the sixth stage, the separation of endosperm pieces from the shell is continued in the products of the first stage.

Each stage and each technological operation is carried out in certain parameters of the machines.

The efficiency of individual machines, technological systems and the entire crushing process is a function of many factors. The main ones are: the quality of initial wheat, the condition of the working bodies of the technological machines (the degree of impermeability of the riffles, the condition of the sieves), the relative humidity of the air, etc.

technological process in the welding department .

- to the processing department ;
- Initial moisture content of wheat;
- Consumption of intermediate products;
- Varieties of flour.

the connecting section is complicated due to the large number of influencing factors and the nonlinearity of individual links.

the connecting section :

- quality indicators of wheat (type, moisture, consumption).

Production parameters : flour quality , output by varieties. Disturbing factors are represented by product features, technological and transport equipment features , microclimate changes in production buildings, voltage fluctuations in the electrical network.

Internal disturbing effects caused by the devices: changes in the characteristics of the internal organs of the machine: bending of the teeth, clogging of the sieve sieves, weakening of the conveyor belts of the machine. Internal disturbing factors related to the change of microclimate of the production rooms affect the character of wheat sifting and grinding.

A change in relative air humidity from 50 to 60% reduces the electrical potential of the sieves from 12000 V to 0.

Disturbances caused by the supply network are associated with $\pm 0.4\%$ fluctuations in voltage and current frequency. The change in the rotation frequency of the asynchronous motor is especially noticeable in sieves.

The control effects of the grinding section are the change of tension between the shafts of the shaft machines, the change of the kinematic parameters of the shaft machine and the screen, and the degree of opening of various adjusting barriers.

Corrective effect is shown on shaft machines and executive mechanisms for operational control.

In flour production enterprises, individual machines, technological blocks, stages, departments and the entire enterprise are the object of management.

The technological blocks used in grain processing plants, i.e., the complex of machines that ensure the execution of the required operation, are almost identical in terms of their functions and adjustment possibilities.

Depending on the type of control object in flour production, the nature of operational control effects is also different. By changing the position of the supply

barriers and the working distance in individual machines and technological blocks, shaft machines, an operational control effect is exerted on the control object.

Control of the technological process in the smelting department is carried out by changing the working mode of the shaft machine-sieve of the technological block, as well as by influencing the input parameters of the object: consumption and quality of raw materials.

The main device of the mill is the controlling effects developed in the crushing department using the shaft machine.

By changing the distance between the shafts, the shaft machine can be controlled operationally. The following kinematic parameters can be varied as well .

- 1) The ratio of the speed of the shafts

$$K = \frac{\vartheta_T}{\vartheta_C}$$

ϑ_T – the speed of the fast rotating shaft

ϑ_C – slow rotating shaft speed

- 2) $\Delta\vartheta = \vartheta_T - \vartheta_C$

$\Delta\vartheta$ – speed difference

The process of milling in a shaft machine is influenced by structural and mechanical properties of wheat, the state of the working surface of the shafts, loading and other factors.

Valli machine work is evaluated according to the dispersed composition of the product passing through the working zone.

The generalized indicator of the granulometric composition of the product - separation A(%) is determined by the ratio of G - the amount of the product passed through a sieve of a certain number to the initial sample mass:

$$A = \frac{G}{m_n}$$

In addition, the work of the shaft machine is evaluated by separate fractions of free energy and the comparative consumption of energy.

The dependence of separation A on the gap between the shafts is expressed exponentially [11]:

$$A = m \cdot e^{-nb}$$

In this case: $m - e$ is the coefficient depending on the product selection conditions in the lacdon analyzer.

n is a coefficient depending on the structural-mechanical properties of wheat and conditions related to grinding conditions.

v - the distance between the shafts (thrust) mm.

The output of individual fractions during grinding is also dependent on the distance between the shafts.

External and internal disturbing effects change the value of n - coefficient to a certain extent.

$A=f(v)$ connection cannot be operationally controlled, because it is impossible to measure the gap between the shafts in the shaft machine during the work process. For him, A - controlling effects are selected according to the main output value of extraction.

The position of the shaft in the technological scheme affects the output of separate fractions depending on the A -separation.

Conclusion. In production conditions, the dependence of A - separation size (%) on Q - fraction output (%) in the first three crushing systems is shown of output quantities on the kinematic parameters of the shaft machine is characterized as follows:

The change in the speed of the fast-rotating shafts has almost no effect on the output and quality of the fractions. Thus, the most real and important of the possible corrective effects for a shaft machine is the change of clearance between the shafts. In the automatic control of roller machines, it is necessary to optimize the output of flour from the sieve being is considered.

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